

Use of Information Communication Technologies (ICTs): For Accessibility of Grey Literature in Medical College Libraries

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Abstract:

Rapid developments of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have changed the conception of traditional libraries. Modern Medical College libraries are more important, dynamic, and can serve without the restrictions of geographical boundaries. In this global period, libraries are fleetly switching to digital mode and are widely accessible. With the arrival of new communication technologies libraries redesigned their services to a borderless world and come the lifeblood of the community. In today's ICT Environment, the Internet has become a major source for spreading and retrieval of grey literature. Well-designed websites offer users access to a body of digitally produced grey literature that complements the existing body of print materials. ICTs are the main source of information retrieval and dissemination system. The Ease of access and the speed, with which large quantities of information can be available, will have implications for science policy shaping and public attitude. This Research paper focuses on the study of Information Communication Technologies (ICTs) to Accessibility of Grey Literature in Medical College Libraries.

Keyword: ICT application; ICT services; Medical library resources; e-learning; grey literature; librarians' role, library

Introduction

Grey Literature "publication" platforms correspond to the multitudinous types of GL producers as described supra. The development of the Internet handed for yet other ways how to make GL available, e.g. on the company or personal websites, blogs, or in the institutional repositories. Standard general search engines (like Google) do not provide for solution of this problem as the GL is located mainly in the "deep web" that is not indexed wholly by them.¹

"Grey Literature is a term used to describe information products which are created and distributed to circulate knowledge (ideas, facts, opinions) rather than to sell for a profit. In practice, and for that reason, Grey Literature is known as information that isn't retailed and distributed by marketable publishing houses. The term 'grey' stems from the fact that such information isn't published and is not available through the traditional channels of publishers and booksellers. "Grey doesn't indicate any qualification; it is merely a characterization of the distribution mode."² "In fact, a large proportion of Grey Literature is distributed in both modes: 'grey' in the form of pre-prints, 'white' in the form of a published article. The quality is often identical; the main difference being that 'white' literature has a quality stamp provided by the publisher and its embedded peer-review process."³

The **value and importance of grey literature** lie substantially in its complexity, topicality, and financial availability. As noted by Schöpfel, and Farace the GL "*represents a substantial part of*

the scientific production".⁴ As the GL is not published in the "traditional way" it logically contains information not available/searchable/indexed by the standard librarian tools (e.g. standard library catalogues). Due to this fact, the GL should be always included in literature searches as it limits the potential bias.⁵ A mere reliance on the officially published sources may lead to a "*subjective one-sided research path*".⁶ The GL also contains more detailed information, an example being a technical report with detailed descriptions, diagrams, and data sets that would be never published in traditional journals.⁷ Compared⁸ to the "white literature" the GL tends to be more up-to-date as it is usually not subject to traditional and time-consuming pre-publishing processes. The quality of GL literature is still debatable⁹ as it is usually not subject quality processes like peer-reviewing in the case of published papers in traditional scientific journals. However, Seymour¹⁰ claims that the grey literature is subject to various levels of internal quality assessment - an example being the review process in the case of master or Ph.D theses. Also, the "publishing's" institution's name and reputation is at stake, therefore a certain quality check is to be expected. Lastly, due to its non-commercial character, the GL is usually available for free as in "free beer"¹¹, i.e. without monetary compensation. As discussed in the next section with the emergence of the Open Access movement the GL is also opening up in the sense of free as in "free speech".

ICT Tools:

ICT tools stand for **Information Communication Technology tools**. The ICT tools mean to digital infrastructures like computers, laptops, printers, scanners, software programs, data projectors, and interactive teaching box. Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have become central to education and training in Library and Information Science/Service (LIS) because of the great influence of these technologies on the professional world.

The arising new technologies have revolutionized the methods of information storage and retrieval in the Medical library field. In this Internet era more and more libraries in the world make use of these new technologies for storage, retrieval, and dissemination of information in a further effective way. Libraries can store a huge quantum of information using new technologies and transmit this information anywhere anytime without any geographical hedge. Scholars fulfill their thrust of information using new technologies without wasting their precious time. ICTs facilitate for rapid transmission of information globally through their networks. It helps library professionals to manage their housekeeping and documentation activities such as circulation, acquisition, maintenance of catalogue, periodical management, etc. in the libraries by automating them. These innovative technologies made accessible platforms for the scholars to make use of the information as well as to explore them. The other automated services in the libraries are storage, dissemination and advance searched for the scholars such as SDI, compiling bibliographies, indexing/abstracting, etc. The traditional library housekeeping methods are now carried by using newer technologies. Newer technologies have given better solutions to most of the problems encountered in the field of libraries related to the acquisition, organization of information, reference services, circulation, and bibliographical services.

Grey Literature @ Medical College Libraries

Medical college libraries produce vast literature, which is not going to publish in the traditionally documents. This literature can be defined as Grey literature. This can be used for research, teaching, and learning. Some institutions, universities issue pre-prints or e-prints before their formal publications and these can be considered as a part of Grey literature. These unpublished Grey literature have potential value to the scholarly community globally. Most of the time, this literature is limited to its creator's desktop and does not have a method to access or

identify globally. Some institutions, universities provide mechanisms to access this information through their academic libraries. This non-conventional collection comprises doctoral dissertations, Annual reports of medical colleges, Reports of clinical trials, Current Controlled Trials, Clinical Study Results WHO Clinical Trials, In-house case-studies or case papers, Patient records, Medical literature given by Medical Representatives (MRs) conference proceeding and papers, scientific reports, etc. Today most of the non-conventional literature can be found in electronic format. In this ICT era libraries do not necessarily to have all the documents in their libraries. Instead of that library professionals should know from where to get what they need. They can access whatever information they need by doing a systematic searches on the web. They should have a direct relationship with the main producers of grey literature.

Objective:

To examine the potential of Information and Communication Technology as a tool to access the Grey literature.

The Rationale for Research Topic

The Librarians of Medical Colleges can play a vital role in bringing together all the Grey literature related to health care. There is a need to disseminate current information from the Grey literature through ICT.

Methodology

For this research, a descriptive method has been used. For collecting data, an Interview method was used.

Tool used for Data Collection

The investigator has used both primary and secondary data for the research work. An Interview method was administered for collecting the required primary data. Secondary data were collected mainly from the brochures, newsletters, records, and different types of publications available in Medical College Libraries.

Scope and Limitations

The Researcher covered Selected MBBS (Government and private) Medical College Libraries for the Study.

Result and Discussion

These days almost the medical college libraries have computerized their cataloguing system. Classification not only brings related documents together, but it also helps in storing and deciding their location. Consider that a medical college library starts with a core collection of GL at some point in its life. Then it is necessary to have an adequate, relevant, comprehensive, and

up-to-date collection of GL which should be accessed when required.

A. Awareness and Organization of GL

Grey literature is not a very new concept. The concept was there, but, not many of the respondents may know that it is called Grey Literature. Some may not have a clear idea regarding the broadness of the concept. Even

they may not be aware of all types of GL. How familiar are the respondents with the organization of GL in their own libraries? These issues are explored in the sub-sections.

B. Awareness of the Concept of Grey Literature

The users were asked whether they had known the concept of Grey literature or not.

Table No. 01, Awareness of Grey Literature

Know the Concept of GL	Faculty	Student	Grand Total
No	6	9	15 (3.75%)
Yes	194	191	385 (96.25%)
Grand Total	200	200	400

The above table shows that Grey Literature was known to the majority i.e., 385 (96.25%) of users, this means that 96.25% of the respondents

had aware of the concept of GL, and the remaining 15 (3.75%) were not aware of GL.

Table No. 02, The Features of GL, Means, and Ranks

Features	Mean of Means	Rank
Ease of Access	3.10	3
Avoids Duplication: Helps Selection of Topics for Research	2.72	7
Teaching Purpose: Extent of Use	1.41	12
Research Purpose: Extent of Use	2.71	8
Up-to-datedness and Recentness	2.61	9
Adequacy and Comprehensiveness	3.20	2
Old GL: Extent of Use	2.73	6
Relevant and need-based GL	2.91	5
Library permits Borrowing	3.02	4
Digitized catalogue Entries	3.37	1
Text-based Access through CD or Server	1.96	10
Facilitating Online Access	1.58	11

Table No. 03, Rank-wise Features

Rank	Features	Mean of Means
1	Digitized catalogue Entries	3.37
2	Adequacy and Comprehensiveness	3.2
3	Ease of Access	3.1
4	Library Permit to Borrow	3.02
5	Relevant and need-based GL	2.91
6	Old GL: Extent of Use	2.73
7	Avoids Duplication: Helps Selection of Topics for Research	2.72
8	Research Purpose: Extent of Use	2.71
9	Up-to-datedness and Recentness	2.61
1	Text-based Access through CD or Server	1.96
11	Facilitating Online Access	1.58
12	Teaching Purpose: Extent of Use	1.41

The table above is self-explanatory. 'Digitized Catalogue', 'Adequate and Comprehensive

Collection' and 'Ease of Access' are the top three ranking features expected of a good GL

collection. These are the minimum requirements expected of a GL collection. 'Text-based Access' and 'Online Access' are the needs at high-end. The other needs are in between and much based on the policy and management of the library in question.

In addition to the above, there are some other expectations of users from the libraries housing the Medical GLs.

Online Access for GL Collection

Library facilities are improving fast and the users expect IT-based services and everything on their desktop. Accordingly, the infrastructure facilities were being installed to help the information seekers. In medical colleges, many of the in-house publications were in digital format. They can be accessed through the Local Area Network or Intranet. The year 2001 and onwards, most of the Medical College Libraries have computerized their cataloguing system. Therefore, a majority of the medical college

libraries are having a computerized catalogue or Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) to assist the users in finding out the GL and the other documents. Library OPAC is an outcome of the automation process. It is useful to access the documents available in the library through LAN or campus network or intranet or it can be uploaded on the web and made searchable. Such web-based access can be provided in today's era.

Online Access to Institutional Publications

The present time is referred to as the electronic age. Automation of library functions and services has become the order of the day. Academic and research institutions have created their websites to host various information services for remote and wider access, breaking the barriers of time and distance. In this direction, libraries have started maintaining websites or servers for hosting information to their users. GL also can be digitally generated, stored, accessed, and disseminated.

Table No. 04, Online Access to Institutional Publications

Sr. No	Online Access to Institutional Publications	Faculty	Students	Total
1	Yes	138	142	280 (70%)
2	No	56	49	105 (26.25%)
3	No Answer	06	09	15 (3.75%)
	Total	200	200	400 (100%)

Above Table No. 04 shows the online access of Institutional Publications including internally generated GL. As it is seen in the chart, 280 users access Institution or Library Websites to see the information about Institutional Publication such as Annual reports, Developmental reports, Budget reports, and In-

house publications, including Newsletters clinical tests, etc., GL. The balance includes 105 users not accessing Institution or Library Websites for Institutional Publications and 15 respondents have remained silent on this issue. These 280 respondents are further categorized as shown the Table 05

Table No. 05, College Libraries Hosting Information on

Sr. No	Responses	Faculty	Students	Total
1	On the Website	39	33	72 (25.71%)
2	In the Intranet Server	99	109	208 (74.29%)
	Total	138	142	280 (100%)

The above table shows that 72 (25.71%) users indicated that they access institution or library websites to see information about Institutional Publications. However, 208 (74.29%) respondents, access the intranet server to see the information about Institutional Publications.

Access to Institutional Publications also is accessible through the web or intranet. Online Access for GL collection is made possible through ICT.

Findings

Institutional publications and annual reports play a vital role in preparing proposals and reports concerning the institution. Considering all medical colleges in Maharashtra, 280 users (70%) (Please see Table No. 04) expect access to the digital version of institutional publications such as annual reports, developmental reports, budget reports, and in-house publications, including newsletters.

As it is seen, 208 respondents out of 280 (74.29%), (Please see Table No. 05.) access the server for the information regarding Institutional

Publications. On the other hand, 72 respondents out of 280 (25.71%) indicated that they access institution or library websites to seek knowledge regarding Institutional Publications. Almost all activities related to scanning websites/databases for relevant GL, identification, selection, ordering, procurement and processing i.e., cataloguing, classification, providing metadata are done through ICT or the internet. Further, the entire text or graphics can be scanned and stored, so that the document can be directly accessed. Besides, these days it is much simpler because all the GL are born digital. Once it is in machine-readable form then it can be subjected to any ICT application. RSS Feed and other 'Alerting Services' are the other major gifts of ICT which help in effortless access to new GL. Today one can search and access directly any GL unless it is an official trade secret or classified Defense related information. ICT helps access full-text of the latest addition of GL. Internet facility and web technology have made it easy to access.

Suggestion

It is with this context that, there is an urgent need to study the existing situation in Medical/Health Colleges/Universities in Maharashtra, especially about the current development of ICTs and the opportunities the national Fiber-optic network is offering to universities in the country. Overall there is a great potential on the ground in terms of ICT possibilities; it is up to Health Universities and the Governments to exploit them to enhance access and use of grey literature.

Conclusion

The holding of GL is an up-to-date collection in the Medical college libraries. However, it is encouraging note that the majority of the users aware of Grey literature and users also use Information Communication Technologies for accessing the GL. Users access the Institution or Library website to see the latest GL e.g. institutional publication, annual reports, clinical tests, etc. through an Internet server. Online access for GL collection is made possible through ICT. Almost all activities related to scanning websites/databases for relevant GL, identification, selection, ordering, procurement and processing i.e., cataloguing, classification, providing metadata are done through ICT or the internet. Thus, ICT helps access the full-text of the latest addition of GL. Internet facility and web technology have made it easy to access.

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